

NONLINEAR ANALYSIS OF MATHIEU-DUFFING OSCILLATOR WITH INTERACTING PARAMETRIC AND EXTERNAL EXCITATION

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Abstract

The study investigates the nonlinear dynamic characteristics of Mathieu-Duffing oscillator with interacting parametric and external excitation. The amplitude and frequency of interacting parametric and external excitation are the control parameters for dynamic analysis. The fourth order Runge-kutta method in MATLAB is utilized for numerical analysis. The dynamic behaviors are analyzed through phase plane and time history. It is observed that at lower values of amplitude of pure parametric excitation, the system shows evolution of periodic attractors and at higher values of amplitude of pure parametric excitation, the system shows evolution of coexisting attractors. The separation between the coexisting attractors decreases with increase in the value of amplitude of parametric excitation. It is also observed that the system shows evolution of multiperiodic attractors at lower value of amplitude of interacting parametric and external excitation. With increase in the values of amplitude of interacting parametric and external excitation, there is evolution of toroidal attractors. With further increase in amplitude and phase angle of interacting parametric and external excitation, there is evolution of coexisting attractors.

Key words: Mathieu Duffing oscillator, Interacting parametric and external excitation, Fourth-Order Runge-kutta Algorithm, Periodic attractor, Multiperiodic attractor, Toroidal attractor, Coexisting attractor.

1. Introduction

The issue of nonlinear oscillations has been studied extensively for years because the nonlinear oscillations concern many physical systems. To the issue of nonlinear oscillations, the Mathieu-Duffing oscillator is inseparably connected. The Mathieu-Duffing oscillator is the standard form of a parametrically excited oscillator having cubic nonlinearity. The parametrically excited oscillators are observed in different fields of science and technology such as atomic physics [1], microwave systems [2], mechanical resonators [3] and optics [4]. The prediction of response of Mathieu-Duffing system with interacting parametric and external excitation is of paramount importance in designing systems such as amplifiers, sensors and energy harvesters. The parametric excitation is generally used in these systems for better amplification leading to enhanced sensitivity. More over, the parametric amplification phenomenon is used to enhance the performance of broadband piezoelectric energy harvester.

Wu et al. [5] studied the dynamic behavior of parametrically excited marine riser under simultaneous stochastic wave force and vortex excitation by stochastic phase spectrum method. Zhou et al. [6] and Thomson et al. [7] studied the parametric roll motion of ships under regular longitudinal waves using Melnikov method and determined the critical conditions of chaos for homoclinic and heteroclinic cycle. Gonzalez-Buelga et al. [8] and Peng et al. [9] studied the stability analysis of cable supported structures subjected to support excitation considering 2:1 internal resonance using rescaling and averaging methods. Kovacic et al. [10] and Nayfeh et al. [11] studied extensively parametrically excited Duffing oscillator. Aghamohammadi et al. [12,13] studied the parametrically excited Duffing oscillator with external excitation using Method of Varying Amplitude (MVA). Torteman et al. [14], Meesala et al. [15] and Zhang et al. [16] studied numerically the micro oscillator based mass sensor subjected to parametric excitation using finite difference method. Xia et al. [17]

and Yildirim et al. [18] studied the frequency response analysis of parametrically excited nonlinear energy harvester considering as piezoelectric beam using Galerkin method. Alevras et al. [19] studied the broad band energy harvesting of nonlinear Mathieu systems. Kuang et al. [20], Dotti et al. [21] and Kumar et al. [22] studied the parametrically excited magnetic rolling nonlinear pendulum on energy harvesting. Abdelkefi et al. [23] and He et al. [24] studied the parametrically excited piezoelectric energy harvester using Euler-Lagrange principle and Gauss Law through Galerkin discretization. Karlicic et al. [25] studied the steady state response of nonlinear piezoelectric energy harvester subjected to external and parametric excitation. Barakat et al. [26] studied the nontrivial solutions at different parametric resonance conditions of Mathieu-Duffing system. Zhang et al. [27] studied the cascaded and noncascaded bursting oscillations of a Mathieu-Vanderpol oscillator under low frequency parametric and external excitation. Abohamer et al. [28] explored the chaotic behaviour of Vanderpol-Mathieu-Duffing oscillator under parametric resonance. Sahoo et al. [29] investigated the dynamics of Vanderpol-Mathieu-Duffing oscillator for different excitation functions using mesh-free Symplectic Artificial Neural network algorithm. Ma et al. [30] studied the generation of symmetric and asymmetric bursting behaviour of a hybrid Vanderpol-Duffing-Rayleigh oscillator with low frequency amplitude modulated excitation.

The literature review reveals that although various researches have been carried out on Mathieu Duffing oscillator, no extensive study has been done on Mathieu Duffing oscillator with interacting parametric and external excitation. Moreover, in the work of Aghamohammadi et al. [13], besides frequency response curve analysis, nontrivial solutions such as periodic, multiperiodic, quasiperiodic, coexisting behavior have not been explored. In order to meet the research gap, the present paper focuses on existence and evolution of various types of nontrivial solutions such as periodic, multiperiodic, toroidal and coexisting behavior are studied. The paper discusses the nontrivial response of Mathieu Duffing oscillator under two cases, one with pure parametric excitation in absence of external excitation and the other with interacting parametric with external excitation.

2. Analytical Model

The Mathieu Duffing oscillator can be modeled as a pendulum swinging under gravity and the support is under combined horizontal and vertical harmonic excitation as illustrated in Figure 1. The differential equation for the Mathieu Duffing oscillator with interacting parametric and external excitation can be expressed as Aghamohammadi et al. [13]

$$\ddot{x} + \alpha \dot{x} + \omega_0^2 [1 + \gamma \cos(\Omega t)] x + \beta x^3 = f \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}\Omega t + \phi\right) \quad (1)$$

where x represents the displacement response of the system, α is the damping ratio, β is the nonlinear coefficient, Ω represents the parametric excitation frequency, ω_0 represents the undamped natural frequency, γ represents amplitude of parametric excitation, f represents the amplitude of external excitation, ϕ is the phase angle between parametric and external excitation. The dot represents derivative with respect to time. The frequency of parametric excitation is two times the frequency of external excitation.

Scaling $f = \varepsilon \tilde{f}$, $\alpha = \varepsilon \tilde{\alpha}$, $\gamma = \varepsilon \tilde{\gamma}$ and dropping the tildes, the equation (1) may be written as a first order form

$$\dot{x} = y \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{y} = -\omega_0^2 x - \beta x^3 + \varepsilon [f \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}\Omega t + \phi\right) - \alpha y - \omega_0^2 \gamma \cos(\Omega t) x] \quad (3)$$

where ε is a very small parameter ($\varepsilon \leq 1$).

Figure 1. Mathieu Duffing Oscillator with interacting parametric and external excitation

The unperturbed system ($\varepsilon = 0$) may be expressed as

$$\dot{x} = y \tag{4}$$

$$\dot{y} = -\omega_0^2 x - \beta x^3 \tag{5}$$

The equation (5) represents a Hamiltonian system whose Hamiltonian function is expressed as

$$H = \frac{1}{2} y^2 + \frac{\omega_0^2}{2} x^2 + \frac{\beta}{4} x^4 \tag{6}$$

The system has two stable equilibrium points and one unstable equilibrium point representing the solution of

algebraic equation $\omega_0^2 x + \beta x^3 = 0$. They are $(0,0)$ and $\left(\pm \sqrt{-\frac{\omega_0^2}{\beta}}, 0\right)$

3. Dynamic response of Mathieu Duffing oscillator considering pure parametric excitation

The governing equation for Mathieu Duffing oscillator considering pure parametric excitation without external excitation ($f = 0$) can be expressed mathematically as

$$\ddot{x} + \alpha \dot{x} + \omega_0^2 [1 + \gamma \cos(\Omega t)] x + \beta x^3 = 0 \tag{7}$$

The dynamic characteristics are numerically investigated applying fourth-order Runge-kutta integration using MATLAB. The initial conditions taken are $x_0 = 0.001, y_0 = 0.001$ with step size of 0.001. The system

parameters taken are $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10$. At lower value of amplitude of parametric excitation $\gamma = 0.01$, the phase plane shows periodic attractor as observed in figure 2. The phase plane represents a closed curve. When the parametric excitation amplitude is increased to $\gamma = 10$, the phase plane shows evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors as illustrated in the figure 3. The trajectories circulate about their own basins of attraction around equilibrium points $(\pm 1.0, 0)$ implying bistability behaviour. When the amplitude of parametric excitation is increased to $\gamma = 20$, the phase plane again shows evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors as illustrated in figure 4 but the separation between the coexisting attractors is decreased. The trajectories circulate about their own basins of attractions around equilibrium points $(\pm 0.6, 0)$.

Figure 2. Phase plane and time history showing periodic attractor under pure parametric excitation for $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \gamma = 0.01$

Figure 3.Phase plane and time history showing evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors under pure parametric excitation at $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \gamma = 10$

Figure 4. Phase plane and time history showing evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors under pure parametric excitation $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \gamma = 20$

As the amplitude of parametric excitation is further increased to $\gamma = 35$, the separation between the coexisting attractors decreases and the trajectories circulate about their own basins of attraction around equilibrium points $(\pm 0.5, 0)$ as illustrated in phase plane trajectory of figure 5. When the amplitude of excitation is further increased to $\gamma = 40$, the separation between the coexisting attractors further decreases and the trajectories circulate around the basins of attraction about equilibrium points $(\pm 0.4, 0)$ as observed in phase plane of figure 6.

Figure 5. Phase plane and time history showing evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors under pure parametric excitation at $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \gamma = 35$

Figure 6. Phase plane and time history showing evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors under pure parametric excitation at $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \gamma = 40$

4. Dynamic response of Mathieu Duffing oscillator with interacting parametric and external excitation

The governing equation for Mathieu Duffing oscillator considering parametric as well as external excitation is given by

$$\ddot{x} + \alpha \dot{x} + \omega_0^2 [1 + \gamma \cos(\Omega t)]x + \beta x^3 = f \cos\left(\frac{1}{2} \Omega t + \phi\right) \tag{8}$$

The dynamic characteristics are numerically investigated applying fourth order Runge-kutta algorithm. The initial conditions taken are $x_0 = 0.001, y_0 = 0.001$ with step size of 0.001. The system parameters taken are $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10$. For amplitude of parametric excitation $\gamma = 0.01$ and amplitude of external excitation $f = 15$ with phase difference $\phi = 0$, the phase plane shows the evolution of period-5

attractors as illustrated in figure 7. Taking system parameters $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10$ when the parametric excitation amplitude is increased to $\gamma = 5$ and external excitation amplitude is increased to $f = 25$ with phase difference $\phi = 0$, the phase plane shows the evolution of toroidal attractors as observed from figure 8.

Figure 7. Phase plane and time history showing period-5 attractors under interacting parametric and external excitation at $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \phi = 0, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \gamma = 0.01, f = 15$

Figure 8. Phase plane and time history showing evolution of toroidal attractors under interacting parametric and external excitation at $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \phi = 0, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \gamma = 5, f = 25$

Considering system parameters $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1, \Omega = 10$, when amplitude of parametric excitation is taken as $\gamma = 20$, and amplitude of external excitation is taken as $f = 25$, and the phase angle $\phi = 60$ there is evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors as observed from phase plane of figure 9. The origin $(0,0)$ is saddle point. The trajectories emanate away from equilibrium point $(0,0)$ towards their own basins of attraction and circulate about equilibrium point $(\pm 0.5, 0)$.

Figure 9.Phase plane and time history showing evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors under interacting parametric and external excitation at $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \phi = 60, \gamma = 20, f = 25$

Keeping the system parameters $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \gamma = 5, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \phi = 60, \gamma = 20$, when the amplitude of external excitation is increased to $f = 35$, the system again shows evolution of coexisting attractors as observed from the phase plane of figure 10 but the separation between the coexisting attractors increases. The equilibrium point $(0,0)$ is a saddle point. All the trajectories emanate away from origin $(0,0)$ towards basins of attraction and move around the equilibrium points $(\pm 0.9, 0)$.

Figure 10.Phase plane and time history showing evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors under interacting parametric and external excitation at $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \phi = 60, \gamma = 20, f = 35$

Considering system parameters $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1, \Omega = 10, \phi = 60, f = 25$, when amplitude of parametric excitation is taken as $\gamma = 30$, again there is evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors as observed from phase plane of figure 11 but the separation between the coexisting attractors decreases. The origin $(0,0)$ is an unstable equilibrium point. The trajectories move away from equilibrium point $(0,0)$ towards their own basins of attraction and circulate about equilibrium point $(\pm 0.1, 0)$.

Figure 11.Phase plane and time history showing evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors under interacting parametric and external excitation at $\alpha = 0.0001, \beta = 0.0005, \omega_0 = 1.0, \Omega = 10, \phi = 60, \gamma = 30, f = 25$

5. Conclusion

The nonlinear dynamic characteristics of Mathieu-Duffing oscillator are investigated with interacting parametric and external excitation. The amplitude as well as frequency of interacting parametric and external excitation are taken as the control parameters for dynamic analysis. Using fourth-order Runge-kutta algorithm in MATLAB, numerical integration is performed. The nonlinear dynamic responses are presented through phase portrait and time trace. The dynamic characteristics are studied under two cases: considering only parametric excitation and the other under combined effect of parametric and external excitation. The following conclusions are drawn from numerical analysis.

1. The dynamic characteristics are dependent on initial conditions.
2. With lower value of amplitude of pure parametric excitation, the system shows evolution of periodic attractors. With higher value of amplitude of pure parametric excitation, the system shows evolution of coexisting attractors and the separation between the coexisting attractors decreases with increase in amplitude of parametric excitation.
3. With lower value of amplitude of interacting parametric and external excitation, the system shows evolution of multiperiodic attractors and with higher values of amplitude of interacting parametric and external excitation, the system shows evolution of toroidal attractors .
4. With further increase in amplitude of interacting parametric and external excitation, the system shows evolution of symmetrical coexisting attractors. The separation between the coexisting attractors increases with increase in amplitude of external excitation and the separation between the coexisting attractors decreases with increase in amplitude of parametric excitation.

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